

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS THE ROPP COMPLEX, NORTH CENTRAL NIGERIA, USING
MAGNETIC ANOMALY AND LANDSAT ETM IMAGERY

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ABSTRACT

A structural investigation of the Ropp Complex was carried out by studying the linear magnetic anomaly that runs through of the Ropp Younger Granite Complex and the Landsat Imagery. Aeromagnetic data and Landsat Imagery taken over the study area were processed using various reduction techniques. These include digitizing, interpolation, filtering, least square regression analysis, contrast stretching and eventually 3D residual magnetic model of the study area was produced. Lineaments extracted from the Landsat ETM imagery showed major NE-SW and minor NW-SE trends. Geological field mapping shows that the Complex is deformed by shearing, faulting and jointing, while the enclosing Basement Complex is foliated. The major structures trend in the NE-SW direction while minor structures trend in the NW-SE direction. The magnetic lineaments are shown as a narrow belt of low anomaly, varying from 3 to 5 km in length. These magnetic features may represent major tectonic trends which continue across the Younger Granite Provinces. Contoured map of the lineament density produced from the gridded lineaments from the enhanced Landsat band 7 imagery tend to show the area of high lineament density, which could be the target area for mineral and hydrogeological exploration. This would also offer quick glance at the spatial distribution of the density of lineament and hence provide database in mineral and hydrogeological exploration.

KEYWORDS: Younger Granite, Magnetic Anomaly, LandSat Imagery, Structural Investigation, Mineral and Hydrogeological Exploration

INTRODUCTION

The Ropp Complex located southeast of the Jos Bukuru Complex in north central Nigeria is known for its whitish riebeckite granites and extensive kaolin and tin mineralization and a long mining history. It was the second largest tin producer in the Nigerian Younger Granite Province (Buchanan et al.1971). The area of interest is located in the southern part of the Ropp Complex and is defined by Latitude 9°18N and 9°30N and by Longitude 8°49E and 9°00E, and covers a total of about 417.6 square kilometers. Geologic structures, even though concealed entirely below the earth's surface, can still be concisely studied and mapped by methods such as aeromagnetic surveys (Ofuoegbu, 1985; Dobrin and Savit, 1988; Iliya and Bassey, 1993; Bozzo et al., 1999; Blakely *et al.*, 2000 and Nur, 2000). Magnetic measurements are usually made from aircraft flown along closely spaced, parallel flight lines covering the region and other adjacent areas, including additional flight lines which are flown in the perpendicular direction to assist in data processing. These measurements then are processed into a digital aeromagnetic map. For this study, aeromagnetic maps were obtained from the Nigerian Geological Survey Agency, from which interpretations are made. The airborne Geophysical Survey map used was flown and compiled by Hunting Geology and Geophysics Limited, produced by the Geological Survey of Nigeria at a scale of 1:100,000 (GSN, 1975).

Geological setting

The Ropp Complex is bounded by an extensive arcuate and polygonal ring dyke which encloses basement rocks and a prominent central massif of rugged Younger Granite hills (Figure 1). Some of the central hills rise more than 300m above the plateau surface and form conspicuous landmarks. Both volcanic and plutonic cycles are distinguished in the Ropp complex. The cycle of the granitic intrusion was initiated by a coarse – grained granite porphyry similar to that of the Jos-Bukuru Complex, followed by a succession of biotite – and riebeckite- granites. Later in the intrusive cycle, there was a recurrence of granite porphyry, hornblende-biotite-granite and late biotite-granites. The volcanic cycle include the quartz porphyries, rhyolite and explosion breccia and early basic dykes (Buchanan et al 1971).

Figure 1. Location map of Ropp Complex (After Buchanan et al, 1971).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Enhancement techniques which include digitizing, interpolation, filtering and least square regression analysis were used for the representation of the aeromagnetic data which was acquired from the Geological Survey Agency of Nigeria. Since the aeromagnetic map was received on paper, it had to be digitized and geo-registered using a geographic to UTM transformation. Contour lines were plotted out and verified for completeness and accuracy. The landSat ETM imagery covering the study area was acquired from the National Centre for Remote Sensing. The imagery is a higher version of landsat TM and was taken by the satellite on 20th of November 2004. The image was processed and analyzed for lineament which may control mineralization. This was followed by ground geological and structural mapping.

The Magnetic anomaly analysis

The total intensity map of the study area was digitized; it has values ranging from 7875 gammas to 7787 gammas (Figure 2) with dominant magnetic value as 7750 gammas (Figure 3). The script slope process applied filters; df/dy and df/dx filter on the digital elevation model created from the contour data. The process was performed on the aeromagnetic data to enhance the structural pattern, in which the high wave number content of the data is enhanced. This produced two output images, the first being the slope component in the E-W (x) direction, the second, the slope component in the N-S (y) direction, these constitute the local first derivatives df/dx and df/dy. They were produced by passing the interpolated data through the Dx and Dy filter respectively. The Dx filter detects slope difference in the X-direction from west to east while the Dy filter detects slope difference in the Y-direction from south to north. This gives positive and negative anomalies respectively. The results (Fig 4 and 5) indicate a general trend of anomalies in the NE - SW directions. However, the object of the investigation is to detect not only with changes along the sequence, but also to identify where these changes occur. To eliminate the regional field, a plane surface was fitted to the data by a polynomial expansion equation (regression least square), where this is the summation of integer's power of the independent variables: Polynomial regional fitting; $Z(x, y) = 7858.48 + (-1.757y)$.

Where x and y are unit spacing of the digitized total magnetic intensity map. This polynomial function produces the linear regional trends (Davies, 1973). These regional field values were subtracted from the observed data, from which the residuals were calculated. A 3D surface model was constructed for the total magnetic intensity and the residual magnetism of the study area of the Ropp complex. The models show a general NE-SW trend across the study area of the Ropp complex (Figure 6 and 7).

Figure 6. 3D model of the total magnetic intensity of the study area after the removal of the regional field. Figure also shows the direction of the dominant structural trends in the NE-SW

Figure 7. 3D model of the residual magnetic intensity of the study area after the removal of the regional field. Figure also shows the direction of the dominant structural trends in the NE-SW direction

Structures of Ropp Complex

Lineaments were extracted from the enhanced Landsat band 7 stretched map (Figure 8). Although there are lineaments of a number of different orientations there appear to be two predominant trends: A major (NE-SW) and minor (NW-SE) lineaments trend. These trends can be distinguished from length frequency rose diagram of the Landsat ETM (Figure 9). Contoured map of the lineament density produced from the gridded lineaments show the area of high lineament density, which could be the target area for mineral exploration (Figure 10). Lineament analysis as applied to mineral exploration attempt to define the most location for mineral concentration, these zones forms channels for easy passage for the mineralizing fluids. Many of the lineaments mapped on the Landsat imagery examined on the ground consisted in part of linear segments of drainage, many of which were also aligned with linear scarps. Along those lineaments which outcrops were located were observed joints, quartz-veins and dykes that parallel the lineaments. This suggests that most of the lineaments mapped are fracture zones.

Structures (which are generally considered as evidence of deformation left as imprints on rocks) in the Complex include joints, veins, dykes, foliations and faults, trend mainly in the NE-SW direction (Figure 11-14, Plate 1-4). There is a major shear zone trending NE-SW cutting across the Complex. This zone was identified (also confirmed from field mapping) from twenty separate location (exposures) along the general trend. (Figure 11-14) also show some minor trends in NW-SE direction which are classified as lineament of lengths below 3Km. On the whole, both trends are in conformity with the trends observed in the Nigerian Basement, which indicate some major structural control from the basement on the granites. These structures are believed to have resulted from intense regional tectonism that preceded and accompanied the emplacement of Older Granites during the Pan-African orogeny which produced a very extensive N-S trend in northern Nigeria, including the study area. Joint systems are observed largely in the granitic outcrops, some of which bear quartz veins in the range of a few centimeters in width. Some pegmatites occurring at Gindi Akwati bear smoky quartz and amazonite, while dykes which are mainly dolerites occur mainly as minor intrusives within the host rocks. The trends of these structural elements always conform to the general structural trends of NE-SW and NW-SE, but the NE-SW direction dominant. There is a preponderance of micro strike-slip faulting with mainly a dextral sense movement in the rocks especially the riebeckite granite at Ruku. The major structural elements found on the basement rocks are foliations and bandings of felsic and mafic components in the rocks and micro strike-slip faults (Plate 2) with mostly dextral movements. These trend generally in the NE-SW direction mainly with some minor NW-SW directional trend.

Figure 8. Enhanced Landsat band 7 image map of the Ropp Complex

Figure 9. Lineament map and rose plot of the Ropp Complex

Figure 10. Contoured lineament density map of the study area.

Figure 11. Rose plots of reading of dykes and veins in the study area with major trend in NE-SW direction.

Figure 12. Rose plots of fractures in the study area with major trend in NE-SW direction.

Figure 13. Rose plot of foliations in the study area with major trend in NE-SW direction.

Figure 14. Lower hemisphere projection of Contour density of pole to foliations in the study area.

DISSUSSION

The NE – SW trending anomalies are dominant magnetic features of the Ropp area, which parallels major structural trends in the Nigeria Younger Granite Province (Ajakaiye et al, 1985). The magnetic lineaments which constitute a narrow belt of low anomaly, extending up to 5 km as its length trends NE – SW (Figure 6 and 7). These magnetic features constitute tectonic lineaments which may represent major tectonic trends that continue across the Younger Granite Provinces. In the Ropp area, the lineaments seem to be concentrated towards the southern part of the Complex. Such areas are potential zones for mineralization (Ashano and

Olasehinde, 2010), and they are underlain mainly by hydrothermally altered biotite-granite plutons in the Younger Granite Province. The structures in north east section of the Nigeria Basement Complex are oriented NE-SW and ENE-WSW mainly and a minor, E-W trend, appear to be in consonance with the alignment of the Younger Granite Complex structure (Rahaman, 1988). These directions are the main structural planes of weakness, which parallels that highlighted by the aeromagnetic analysis of the Ropp area. Since these structural trends are parallel to direction of regional alignment of the Younger Granite Ring Complexes, these Basement trends may have guided the emplacement of the granites during the Jurassic. Lineament density analysis have been the stock in trade in most geological applications of structural controls to mineralization such that points of intersections and trends are usually sort after in explorations. Hence, zones where these lineaments intersect or cross rock boundaries constitute valuable target areas during mineral exploration (Ashano and Olasehinde, 2010). Contoured map of the lineament density produced from the gridded lineaments from the enhanced LandSat band 7 imagery (Figure 9) tend to show the area of high lineament density, which could be the target area for mineral exploration (Figure 10). This is particularly advantageous in modern exploration geosciences in that they offer quick glance at the spatial distribution of the density of lineament and hence provide database in mineral exploration.

Also, for the Nigerian Younger Granites to be characterized by a dominant alkaline trend geochemically, in a manner similar to those obtained in Kola Peninsula, East African Rift System (Ashano and Umeji, 2010), fracturation in the North Eastern segment of Nigerian Basement Complex must be very deep. The fracture pattern are believed to have been established before the emplacement of the ring complexes developed as high level magma chambers beneath them, thus lending support to the assumption that these direction are outward prolongation of deep seated fracture zones that limited and guided the location of the Younger Granite eruptions and large intrusive masses like Jos-Bukuru Complex (Ike, 1983). Tin mineralization in the Younger Granite Province is almost confined to the biotite-granites. Detailed mapping of the biotite-granite has revealed that the mineralized greisens and quartz veins are concentrated near the roofs of intrusions and that the richest alluvial concentrations are found only in the vicinity of, or on the drainage system from granite intrusion which have undergone shallow erosion. Topaz, beryl, genthelvite, wolfram and sulphides occur in the greisens and quartz veins (Buchanan *et al.*, 1971). The mineralogy of the province is typically alkaline thus, lending credence to the reference and suggestion being made in this work.

The areas of high lineament density and weathering could also be target area for hydrogeological investigation, since these two properties are indispensable for ground water aquifer in Basement Complex rocks. (Obiefuna, *et al.*, 2010).

Plate 1. A dolerite dyke about 1km in length and 150cm in width at Yelwa trending N 25°E

Plate 2. A micro fault on the Riebeckite-biotite- granite at Tenti

Plate 3. Joints network on biotite granite at Bukka Bokwai

Plate 4. Quartz vein within the granite porphyry at Gindi Akwai

Plate 5. Small scale mining of accessory minerals associated kaolin alteration along fracture zones at Major Porter

CONCLUSION

Incorporating the structural evidence from the residual aeromagnetic data and lineaments from the Landsat ETM imagery tend to define the tectonic nature and geological features that could be related to the mineralization in the Ropp complex. These features provide pathways for the mineralizing fluid from source to the site of deposition. These geological features may then be used to develop predictive mapping for both mineral and hydrogeological potential of the Ropp complex.

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